

PREPARATION OF SOME 3-ARYL-2-ARYLIMINOTHIAZOLID-4-ONES AND THEIR DERIVATIVES

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Five 3-aryl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones have been prepared by condensing *S*-diarylthioureas with monochloroacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate; their 5-benzylidene and 5-(*p*)-sulphonamidophenylazo derivatives have also been described.

The importance of thiazolidone compounds as potent medicinals and amoebicidal agents has encouraged the author to synthesise several 3-aryl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones and prepare their derivatives. The present work is in continuation with the earlier work of Bhargava (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 2353) and Bhargava *et al.* (*this Journal*, 1955, 32, 49, 763).

In the present investigation five different 3-aryl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones have been prepared according to the procedure adopted in the preparation of 3-*o*-anisyl-2-*o*-anisyliminothiazolid-4-one (vide Experimental).

The thiazolidone compounds, prepared above, were condensed with benzaldehyde in glacial acetic acid medium in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate for the preparation of the 5-benzylidene derivatives of the thiazolidones, but it was found that due to the presence of acidic medium, some thiazolidones were hydrolysed to thiazolid-2:4-diones, and both these compounds reacted with benzaldehyde to form their benzylidene derivatives. As the separation of these derivatives was very difficult, it was thought best to avoid the use of acidic medium, and the thiazolidone compounds were refluxed with an excess of benzaldehyde without any solvent, using pyridine as the condensing agent. The derivatives, thus prepared, had no chance to be contaminated with benzylidene derivatives of the corresponding thiazolid-2:4-diones. Further, the thiazolidone compounds have been coupled with diazotised sulphanilamide to give rise to 5-(*p*)-sulphonamidophenylazo derivatives. The fact that the azo group is attached to the reactive methylene group at position 5 of the thiazolidone nucleus has been reported earlier (Rout, *this Journal*, 1955, 32, 563; Bhargava *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1956, 33, 596).

EXPERIMENTAL

S-Diarylthioureas were obtained by the conventional method of Rathke (*Ber.*, 1873, 8, 799). In the preparation of *S*-di-*o*-chlorophenylthiourea, the yield obtained was very small due to the formation of *o*-chloroaniline salt of phenylthiocarbamic acid of the formula $C_6H_4Cl.NH.CS.SH(NH_2.C_6H_4Cl)$ (Grosch, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 1088). However, after washing several times with hot water, the latter was dissolved out and the pure thiourea left over. Similarly *S*-di-*m*-chlorophenylthiourea was also obtained in low yield.

3-*o*-Anisyl-2-*o*-anisyliminothiazolid-4-ones.—5-Di-*o*-anisylthiourea (3.6 g.) was heated under reflux with monochloroacetic acid (1.5 g.) in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate (1.6 g.) and absolute alcohol (20-25 c.c.) on a water-bath for 4 hours. The reaction mixture was then poured in water, when a precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed several times with boiling water, and finally recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 197°, yield 80%. The analytical results of this and other thiazolidones are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

3-Aryl (R)-2-aryl (R)-iminiothiazolid-4-ones.

Compd. No.	Nature of R.	Formula.	M.P.	% Yield.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
1	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	157°	80	8.93	8.53
2	<i>o</i> -Phenetyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂ S	119-19°	82	8.05	7.86
3	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	170-71°	68	7.97	8.30
4	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	135°	76	8.11	8.30
5	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl*	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	165°	85	8.09	8.30

* Dains, Irvin and Harrel (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 613) also report its m.p. as 165°.

5-Benzylidene-3-*o*-anisyl-2-*o*-anisyliminothiazolid-4-one.—The preceding 3-*o*-anisylthiazolidone (1 g.) and benzaldehyde (1.5 c.c.) were refluxed in presence of pyridine (5 c.c.) in an oil-bath at 150-60° for 5 to 6 hours. The clear solution thus obtained, was cooled and HCl (dil.) was added to it in excess, when a precipitate was obtained. After shaking well and allowing the precipitate to stand overnight, the greenish yellow precipitate was filtered off, washed with hot water several times till free from acid, and finally it was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 160°, yield 84%. The properties and analytical results are reported in Table II.

TABLE II

5-Benzylidene-3-aryl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones.

Compd. No.	Formula.	Colour.	M.P.	% Yield.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
1	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂ S	Greenish yellow	160°	84	6.65	6.73
2	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	Brownish grey	143-44°	58	6.50	6.30
3	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	Pale grey	169-70°	75	6.81	6.58
4	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	Yellow	172°	70	6.74	6.58
5	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S*	Greenish yellow	212	92	6.90	6.58

* Also prepared by Dains *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), m.p. 213°.

5-(p)-Sulphonamidophenylazo-3-o-anisyl-2-o-anisyliminothiazolid-4-one.—Sulphanilamide (0.56 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (5 c.c.), HCl (conc., 5 c.c.) and water (10 c.c.). This was kept in an ice-bath and diazotised with sodium nitrite (0.5 g.) in minimum quantity of water. The diazotised sulphanilamide was added slowly to a precooled solution of *3-o-anisyl-2-o-anisyliminothiazolid-4-one* (0.5 g.) in acetone (5 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (12-15 c.c.) with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred for 15 minutes more and then poured on ice, contained in a beaker, and shaken well. The beaker was kept aside overnight when a bright yellow precipitate came out. It was filtered, washed with hot water, dried and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 183°, yield 57%. The properties and analytical data are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

5-(p)-Sulphonamidophenylazo-3-aryl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones.

Compd. No.	Formula.	Colour.	M.P.	% Yield.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
1	$C_{22}H_{21}O_5N_5S_2$	Bright yellow	183°	57	13.56	13.69
2	$C_{25}H_{28}O_5N_5S_2$	Deep „	145-50° (decomp.)	62	13.12	12.98
3	$C_{21}H_{15}O_3N_5Cl_4S_2$	Light yellow	168°	53	13.59	13.46
4	$C_{21}H_{15}O_3N_5Cl_2S_2$	Deep orange	125°	69	12.98	13.46
5	$C_{21}H_{15}O_3N_5Cl_2S_2$	Brown-yellow	156-58°	61	13.60	13.46

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